

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No6(5)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 240 sahifa,
16-iyun, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Woosyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – "Yangi O'zbekiston" va "Pravda Vostoka" gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Tinglovchilarga axloqiy-estetik tarbiya berishda notiqlik madaniyatini shakllantirishning samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlari	10
Fazliddin Abdunabiyevich Abdurazaqov	
Professor-o'qituvchilarning ilmiy-pedagogik salohiyatini xalqaro mezonlar asosida rivojlantirish yo'llari	15
Maxmudov Qudratbek Shavkat o'g'li	
Orfografik kompetensiyaning mohiyati va boshlang'ich sinflarda shakllanish bosqichlari	21
Abduvaliyeva Nodira Alisherovna, Mo'minjonova Gulnoraxon Abdupatto qizi	
Tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishda uch o'lchamli vizualizatsiyalarning boshlang'ich ta'limdagi ahamiyati	25
Nabijonova Feruza Valijon qizi	
Loyiha texnologiyasi asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda ijtimoiy tashabbuskorlikni rivojlantirish mazmuni	28
O'rinova Nilufar Muxammadovna	
Sinfdan tashqari o'qish darslarida badiiy asar bilan ishlashning kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosidagi metodikasi	32
Qilichova Billura Yorqinxuja qizi, Homidov H. K.	
Kasbiy-kommunikativ madaniyat fenomenining pedagogik talqini va rivojlanish tendensiyalari	37
Tashpulatova Nodira Olimjon qizi	
Tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishda kompetensiyaviy yondashuv	41
Umbarova Nasiba Xolboy qizi	
Xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda shaxs nutqining shakllanishida psixolingvistikaning ahamiyati	44
Ahmedov Shavkat Asadilloevich, Ataboev Navruz Ihombek o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida matnni tushunish va tahlil qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi (PIRLS dasturi misolida)	47
Abduraxmanova Charos Burxanovna	
Lesson Planning in English Language Teaching at Technical Universities	51
Aitbaeva Nursuliu Tairbekovna	
Lingvistik intellekt asosida individual o'qitish yondashuvining samaradorligi	55
Allanazarova Sadoqat Azimovna	
Xorij tadqiqotlarida zamonaviy oila transformatsiyasida farzandlar taraqqiyotining ijtimoiy-psixologik asoslari	59
Bo'riyeva Mahbuba Shavkatovna	
Теоретико-методологические подходы к изучению эмоциональных концептов в литературе: (на материале английских и немецких фразеологизмов)	63
Сайёра Улашевна Тагаева, Азиза Анкаевна Уразкулова	
The Importance of Forming a Schedule for High School Students	67
D. T. Atabayeva, X. I. Abduraymova	
Milliy cholg'u ansambllari orqali o'quvchilar musiqiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirish	70
Dadamirzayeva Gulshanoy To'lanjon qizi	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyaga yondashuvning texnologik xususiyatlari ...	75
Jumanov Sherzod Saloyevich	
Adabiyot darsliklari uchun yangi o'zbek adabiyoti namunalarini saralashning ilmiy-metodik asoslari	78
Musaboyeva Zulfira Iqboljon qizi	
Maktab geometriyasida ko'pyoqlilar mavzusini o'rganishning innovatsion usullari	83
Pirlepesov Umrbek Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Generativ AI vositalarining mustaqil ta'lim jarayonidagi didaktik funksiyalari	86
Qahramonova Xumora Qahramonovna	
O'quvchi-sportchilar uchun individual mashg'ulot yuklamalarini avtomatik rejalashtirish va optimallashtirish imkoniyatini yaratish ahamiyati	91
Qosimov Faxriddin Jo'raqulovich	

Когнитивный диссонанс как социально-психологический феномен в контексте высшего образования: теоретический анализ	95
Мансурова Гульмира Рафазловна	
Регуляторный произвол или необходимый порядок? Влияние новых регуляторных механизмов на свободу расследовательской журналистики	101
Рауфова Озода	
Qizlar tarbiyasida mahalla–oila–maktab hamkorligi mexanizmlari	105
Choriyeva Dildora Ismat qizi	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini individuallashtirishning samaradorligi: kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida	109
Tangriyev Abdulkarim Tovashevich	
O'qish savodxonligi darslarida matn bilan ishlash orqali o'quvchilarda muammoli vaziyatlarni hal etish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi.....	114
Boymurodova Nodirabegim Bahodir qizi	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida STEAM ta'limi orqali talabalarda tanqidiy fikrlash kompetensiyasini shakllantirish	120
Kozimova Mehriniso Akbarali qizi	
Oliy ta'limda kvest texnologiyasi yordamida fizika fanining murakkab tushunchalarini o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish metodikasi.....	125
O'rinboyeva Kumushoy Sultonbek qizi	
Tasvirlarga raqamli ishlov berish texnologiyalari va ularning amaliy qo'llanilishi	129
Sharipov Nodir Botir o'g'li	
Management of Medical Emergencies in Outpatient Dental Clinics.....	133
Adurazzoqov Kamoliddin, Umarov Maruf, Buzrukhoda Javohir	
Psixologik farovonlikning asosiy komponentlari, ta'sir qiluvchi omillar va zamonaviy baholash usullari	138
Aliyev Samariddin Murotali o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	142
Boymurodova Sadoqat Istam qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi ta'lim tizimi.....	146
Gadoymurodova Kamola Sunnatulloevna	
Oilada bola tarbiyasining ahamiyati va uning shaxs kamolotiga ta'siri	151
Galdiyeva Mehribon Durdiyevna, Oilimova Mushtariy Xaydarali qizi	
Art-pedagogika vositasida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida estetik dunyoqarashni shakllantirishning pedagogik ahamiyati	154
Gulboyev Akbar Tuxtyayevich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ma'naviy tadbirlar orqali vatanparvarlik tuyg'usini shakllantirish	158
Homidov Husniddin Kupaysinovich, Yusupova Gulzor Yunusjon qizi, Norbekova Sevinch Musurmon qizi	
Bone-Grafting Materials in Oral Surgery: Classification, Biological Properties, and Clinical Application	161
Jumaqulova Mashhura Alishevovna, Buzrukhoda Javohir Davronovich	
Mediatsiya va o'qib tushunish kompetensiyasi o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqadorlik	166
Karimova Dilyoraxon Raximjon qizi	
Using STEM Technologies to Foster Rational Thinking in the Dentistry	169
Khonimqulov Javlon, Burkhonova Zarafuz	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini montessori metodikasi vositasida til o'rganish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish usullari modeli.....	173
Mahbuba Yusupova Rustam qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda tayanch kompetensiyalarni integrativ yondashuv asosida shakllantirish metodikasining samaradorligi.....	177
Nasimova N. Q.	
Analysis of Scanning Techniques Used in Orthodontic Dentistry	182
Nasrullayev Javlonbek Ta'atonovich, Rahimberdiyev Rustam Abdunosirovich	
Zamonaviylik - ta'lim konsepsiyasida asosiy mezon sifatida	187
Ochilova Gulnoza Odilovna	

MUNDARIJA SOÐERJANIE CONTENTS

O'qish savodxonligi darslarida xalq og'zaki ijodidan foydalanish metodikasi	191
<i>Qahhorova Sojida Bahodir qizi, Zokirov Javoxir G'aybullo o'g'li</i>	
Diqqat va xotira jarayonlarida raqamli texnologiyalarning roli	196
<i>Salomova Nargiza Sattorovna</i>	
Talabalarda kasbiy refleksiya rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi psixologik omillarning empirik tahlili.....	200
<i>Shukurova Nargiza Ikramovna</i>	
Gimnastikachi qizlarda egiluvchanlik jismoniy sifatini rivojlantirish jarayonida shikastlanishlarning oldini olish	205
<i>Sultanova Musharafxon Xudoyqul qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda ekologik bilimlarni raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida rivojlantirish...	210
<i>Sayfedinova Dildora Ikramitdinovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning rivojlanishida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan texnologiyalardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, imkoniyatlari va yo'nalishlari	216
<i>Uralova Nurxon Maxadovna</i>	
Naqshbandiya qadriyatlarini bo'lg'usi o'qituvchi shaxsini shakllantirishdagi o'rni.....	220
<i>Xalmuxamedova Maxbuba Aslanovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari	223
<i>Xo'jamberdiyeva Maftuna Norqobilovna, Sanaqulova Sevinch Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Developing Logical Thinking via the Use of STEM Technology	226
<i>Yarmuhammedov Nabijon Navruzovich, Burkhonova Zarafuz</i>	
Jismoniy tarbiya darslarida innovatsion metodlardan foydalanishning ahamiyati	229
<i>Yo'ldoshboyeva Zulfiya Ravshan qizi, Jumayev Abdilxakim Turdiyevich</i>	
Значение предмета физического воспитания и спортивной метрологии в физическом воспитании молодежи	233
<i>Маматкулов Равшанжон Солижонович</i>	
Аксиологические аспекты диалога культур в романе Сухбата Афлатуни "Рай Земной"	237
<i>Чернова Татьяна Алексеевна, Худойназаров Сардорбек</i>	

MANAGEMENT OF MEDICAL EMERGENCIES IN OUTPATIENT DENTAL CLINICS

Adurazzoqov Kamoliddin

Umarov Maruf

2nd-Year Clinical Residents of the Department of Dental Implantology

Buzruzkoda Javohir

PhD Scientific adviser:

Samarkand state medical university, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Abstract: This study aimed to assess the prevalence of medical emergencies during outpatient dental treatment and to systematize evidence-based pharmacological and resuscitation protocols for their management. A retrospective analysis of 1,500 patient records was conducted alongside surveys of clinicians and patients. Medical emergencies were identified in 95 cases (6.33%), with the highest incidence observed among female patients over 60 years of age. The most common emergencies included hypertensive crises, collapse, angina pectoris attacks, allergic reactions, and hemorrhage. Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) algorithms and pharmacological management protocols for cardiac, hypertensive, glycaemic, epileptic, and syncopal emergencies were reviewed and systematized. The findings highlight the importance of mandatory pre-treatment screening, blood pressure monitoring, and continuous emergency preparedness training for dental professionals to ensure patient safety and improve clinical outcomes.

Key words: outpatient dentistry, medical emergencies, anaphylactic shock, hypertensive crisis, syncope, cardiopulmonary resuscitation, dental anxiety, emergency drug kit.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot stomatologik ambulator qabul jarayonida yuzaga keladigan shoshilinch tibbiy holatlarning tarqalishini baholash hamda ularni boshqarish bo'yicha dalillarga asoslangan farmakologik va reanimatsion protokollarni tizimlashtirishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot doirasida 1500 nafar bemorning tibbiy hujjatlari retrospektiv tahlil qilinib, shifokorlar va bemorlar o'rtasida so'rovnoma o'tkazildi. Natijalarga ko'ra, 95 ta (6,33%) shoshilinch holat qayd etilgan bo'lib, ularning aksariyati 60 yoshdan oshgan ayol bemorlarda kuzatilgan. Eng ko'p uchragan holatlar gipertonik kriz, kollaps, stenokardiya xuruji, allergik reaksiyalar va qon ketish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan. Tadqiqotda yurak-qon tomir, gipertenziv, glikemik, epileptik va sinkopal holatlar uchun kardiopulmonar reanimatsiya hamda dori vositalaridan foydalanish algoritmlari tizimlashtirildi. Olingan natijalar stomatologik amaliyotda bemorlarni oldindan skrining qilish, arterial bosimni nazorat qilish va shoshilinch yordam ko'rsatish bo'yicha mutaxassislar tayyorgarligini kuchaytirish zarurligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: ambulator stomatologiya, shoshilinch tibbiy holatlar, anafilaktik shok, gipertonik kriz, sinkopa, kardiopulmonar reanimatsiya, stomatologik xavotir, shoshilinch dori vositalari to'plami.

Аннотация: Данное исследование направлено на оценку распространённости неотложных медицинских состояний в условиях амбулаторного стоматологического приёма, а также на систематизацию доказательно обоснованных фармакологических и реанимационных протоколов их ведения. В рамках исследования был проведён ретроспективный анализ 1500 медицинских карт пациентов, а также анкетирование врачей и пациентов. Из 1500 изученных случаев неотложные состояния были зарегистрированы у 95 пациентов (6,33 %), причём наибольшая частота отмечалась среди женщин старше 60 лет. Наиболее распространёнными осложнениями являлись гипертонический криз, коллапс, приступ стенокардии, аллергические реакции и кровотечения. Были систематизированы алгоритмы сердечно-лёгочной реанимации и медикаментозной помощи при кардиологических, гипертензивных, гликемических, эпилептических и синкопальных состояниях. Полученные результаты подтверждают необходимость обязательного предоперационного скрининга, контроля артериального давления и регулярной подготовки стоматологического персонала по оказанию неотложной помощи.

Ключевые слова: амбулаторная стоматология, неотложные состояния, анафилактический шок, гипертонический криз, синкопе, сердечно-лёгочная реанимация, стоматологическая тревожность, набор препаратов для экстренной помощи.

INTRODUCTION

According to the research of K.A. Popova, acute dental and systemic complications remain a significant challenge in modern dental practice. Among these, anaphylactic shock represents one of the most dangerous conditions, often leading to fatal outcomes if not managed promptly. In addition, a variety of other acute medical

conditions may arise during dental procedures, requiring immediate and well-coordinated medical intervention.

The clinical significance of intraoperative medical emergencies has increased substantially due to the rapid expansion of outpatient dentistry and the growing number of elderly patients with complex medical histories. Outpatient dental clinics, once considered relatively low-risk environments, are now recognized as settings where sudden, severe, and potentially life-threatening emergencies may occur. Recent studies indicate that severe psychological stress, painful perioperative stimuli, pre-existing systemic diseases, and the pharmacological risks associated with local anesthetic administration collectively create a multifactorial trigger for acute somatic deterioration in the dental chair (Malamed, 2015).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The Sympathoadrenal Cascade and Psychological Stress

Dental anxiety remains highly prevalent across different patient populations and represents a fundamental factor in the pathophysiology of intraoperative complications. Psychological stress strongly activates the sympathoadrenal system, resulting in a rapid increase in circulating endogenous catecholamines, particularly adrenaline and norepinephrine. In healthy individuals, this physiological response typically manifests as transient tachycardia and a moderate elevation in blood pressure. However, in patients with underlying cardiovascular disease, the same acute stress response may become a significant precipitating factor for serious medical emergencies.

Studies conducted by contemporary researchers have demonstrated that dental anxiety commonly contributes to acute hypertensive crises and angina pectoris attacks by substantially increasing myocardial oxygen demand (Popova, 2022). Furthermore, exogenous vasoconstrictors contained in local anesthetic solutions may precipitate severe tachyarrhythmias, acute coronary syndrome (ACS), or cerebrovascular accidents when inadvertently injected intravascularly or rapidly absorbed in highly stressed patients.

Syncope and Vascular Collapse in the Dental Operatory

Acute vascular collapse and vasovagal syncope account for a considerable proportion of all documented medical emergencies in outpatient dental practice. Vasovagal syncope is primarily described in the literature as a psychogenic neurocardiogenic response to acute fear, sensory discomfort, or needle phobia. This response results in marked bradycardia and systemic vasodilation, ultimately leading to transient cerebral hypoperfusion.

While classic vasovagal syncope is generally self-limiting and resolves after placing the patient in a supine position, true vascular collapse represents a more severe failure of peripheral vascular resistance mechanisms. Evidence suggests that prolonged collapse in the dental setting requires immediate venous access, active fluid resuscitation, and targeted pharmacological support, including glucocorticoids such as prednisolone and peripheral vasoconstrictors such as phenylephrine, to counteract severe distributive or cardiogenic hypotension (Guler et al., 2018).

Gender Vulnerabilities and Geriatric Predisposition

The number of elderly patients seeking advanced endodontic treatment, dental implantology, and extensive oral rehabilitation continues to increase. Aging is inherently associated with progressive structural and functional changes in the cardiovascular, endocrine, and autonomic nervous systems.

According to current scientific literature, elderly patients—particularly those over the age of 60 with essential hypertension, ischemic heart disease, or diabetes mellitus—constitute the highest-risk group in contemporary dental practice (Matsura, 2020). Age-related arterial stiffness, impaired baroreceptor sensitivity, and reduced cardiac reserve make these individuals particularly susceptible to acute stress-induced hemodynamic instability. Recent epidemiological evidence further indicates that elderly female patients demonstrate a higher incidence of intraoperative hypertensive episodes and subsequent vascular instability during invasive dental procedures.

Protocols for Anaphylaxis and Immediate Hypersensitivity

Among all potential complications encountered in dental practice, immediate (Type I) hypersensitivity reactions leading to anaphylactic shock pose the greatest threat to patient survival. In outpatient dentistry, anaphylaxis is most commonly associated with exposure to specific local anesthetics (particularly ester-type agents or preservatives such as methylparaben), antibiotics, latex proteins, or specialized dental biomaterials (Becker, 2010).

The underlying pathophysiological mechanism involves extensive IgE-mediated degranulation of mast cells and basophils, resulting in the systemic release of histamine, leukotrienes, and prostaglandins. Consequently, patients may rapidly develop severe vasodilation, increased capillary permeability, bronchospasm,

and laryngeal edema. International resuscitation guidelines unanimously recognize immediate administration of epinephrine (1 mg/mL) via the intramuscular route as the definitive first-line treatment. This intervention must never be delayed, as anaphylactic shock can progress within minutes to complete airway obstruction and catastrophic circulatory collapse.

Pharmacological Kit Optimization and Emergency Preparedness

Despite the well-documented risks associated with systemic complications, global studies continue to reveal substantial deficiencies in the practical preparedness of dental practitioners. Frequently reported shortcomings include unstandardized or expired emergency drug kits, inadequate availability of airway management devices such as Guedel airways and positive-pressure ventilation masks, and insufficiently practiced cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) protocols among dental teams.

Contemporary clinical guidelines strongly advocate a preventive approach that includes mandatory pre-appointment screening, anxiety-reduction premedication protocols, and strict adherence to standardized pharmacological algorithms. To ensure patient safety and effective emergency management, outpatient dental clinics should maintain fully equipped emergency kits containing essential medications such as epinephrine, prednisolone, phenylephrine, captopril, and hypertonic glucose.

Methods and Materials

To achieve this objective, a comprehensive analysis of medical publications, scientific articles, dental patient records, and the results of structured surveys conducted among both dental practitioners and patients was performed. A total of 1,500 dental patient charts were retrospectively reviewed to identify the incidence and specific types of emergency conditions encountered during dental visits.

Results and Discussion

Statistical Analysis of Emergency Cases

The analysis of 1,500 patient charts revealed the occurrence of acute medical emergencies in 95 individuals. Among these patients, a higher prevalence was observed in females (55 patients) than in males (40 patients). The mean age of the affected individuals was 60.6 years.

The clinical distribution of documented emergencies was as follows:

1. Hypertensive crisis - 38.9% of cases;
2. Vascular collapse - 23.6% of cases;
3. Angina pectoris attacks - 12.6% of cases;
4. Allergic reactions - 12.6% of cases;
5. Hemorrhage (bleeding) - 9.47% of cases;
6. Acute myocardial infarction and stroke - 1.05% of cases;
7. Anaphylactic shock - 1.05% of cases (diagnosed in one patient).

Further evaluation of dental records demonstrated that women over 60 years of age exhibited a greater predisposition to these acute conditions, accounting for 58% of all documented emergency cases.

Emergency Management and Resuscitation Protocols

To effectively manage acute medical emergencies, dental practitioners must strictly adhere to established clinical guidelines. Emergency management should begin with immediate cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) and airway stabilization if the patient is unresponsive.

1. Airway Management: Remove any foreign material or secretions from the oropharynx and extend the patient's neck.
2. Jaw-Thrust Maneuver: Advance the mandible forward and upward to maintain airway patency.
3. Guedel Airway Insertion: Insert the oral airway along the hard palate with the convex side depressing the tongue. Rotate the airway 180° after passing the tongue and advance it until the flange rests against the patient's lips.
4. Ventilation: Deliver two rapid rescue breaths without delay.
5. Chest Compressions: Perform closed-chest cardiac massage at a ratio of 30 compressions to 2 ventilations, maintaining continuous cycles according to CPR guidelines.

- Epinephrine Administration: In cases of cardiac arrest or profound shock, administer epinephrine solution (0.1%, 1 mg/mL) sublingually or intravenously every 5 minutes as indicated.

Specific Pharmacological Protocols for Systemic Emergencies

- Epileptic Seizures:** Immediately summon an emergency medical team. Ensure airway patency, remove any intraoral foreign objects, and position the patient laterally to prevent tongue obstruction and aspiration. Following cessation of convulsions, assess pulse and blood pressure. Administer Phenazepam (Elzepam) 10 mg intravenously, diluted in 10 mL of sterile 0.9% sodium chloride solution, at a maximum injection rate of 3 mL/min.
- Acute Coronary Syndrome (ACS):** Position the patient in a semi-reclined posture with the head elevated, measure blood pressure, and contact emergency medical services. Administer Nitroglycerin 0.4 mg sublingually every 5 minutes (maximum of three doses), while continuously monitoring heart rate and blood pressure. Discontinue Nitroglycerin if systolic blood pressure falls below 90/60 mmHg. If ischemic chest pain persists for longer than 10 minutes, instruct the patient to chew 250-300 mg of acetylsalicylic acid (Aspirin). For analgesia, slowly administer 2 mL of a 50% Analgin (Metamizole) solution diluted in 10 mL of normal saline intravenously. In the absence of contraindications, administer Propranolol (Anaprilin) 10-40 mg sublingually. Contraindications include bronchial asthma, bradycardia (heart rate <60 beats/min), and hypotension (systolic blood pressure <90 mmHg). Arrange immediate hospitalization.
- Hyperglycemic Coma:** Urgently summon an emergency medical team. If signs of hypovolemic shock are present (systolic blood pressure <70 mmHg), initiate intravenous infusion of 0.9% sodium chloride solution at 20 mL/kg body weight per hour. Hospitalize the patient immediately after stabilization.
- Hypoglycemic Coma:** Immediately contact emergency medical services. If the patient remains conscious and able to swallow, administer fast-acting oral carbohydrates. If coma develops, administer an intravenous bolus of 40-60 mL of a 40% glucose solution.
- Hypertensive Crisis:** Reassure the patient and place them in a comfortable head-elevated position. Contact emergency services, monitor pulse and blood pressure, and determine whether routine antihypertensive medication has been taken. Administer Captopril (Capoten) 25 mg sublingually. If the therapeutic response is insufficient after 30 minutes, repeat the dose once. If blood pressure remains elevated, administer Nifedipine (Corinfar) 10-20 mg sublingually, which may also be repeated after 30 minutes if necessary. In cases accompanied by tachycardia, administer Propranolol (Anaprilin) 10-40 mg sublingually. Absolute contraindications include bronchial asthma and bradycardia.

Syncope (Fainting):

- Place the patient in a supine position and elevate the lower extremities.
- Perform gentle massage of the limbs.
- Ensure airway patency and provide adequate ventilation or fresh air.
- Stimulate respiratory and vasomotor centers using a 10% aqueous ammonia solution or by splashing cold water on the face.

If syncope persists, summon an emergency medical team. Administer 1 mL of a 20% sodium caffeine benzoate solution intramuscularly. If ineffective, slowly inject 0.1-0.5 mL of a 1% Phenylephrine (Mesaton) solution diluted in 20 mL of 0.9% sodium chloride intravenously.

Vascular Collapse: Contact emergency medical services immediately. Position the patient supine with elevated legs, ensure adequate ventilation, and maintain body warmth. Confirm airway patency and continuously monitor blood pressure and heart rate. Establish venous access and administer Prednisolone 60-90 mg intravenously as a bolus, followed by infusion of 400 mL of 0.9% sodium chloride solution. Subsequently administer 1 mL of 1% Phenylephrine (Mesaton) via intravenous infusion.

Anaphylactic Shock: Immediately summon a specialized resuscitation team. Position the patient supine with elevated lower limbs and maintain body warmth. Ensure airway patency. Administer 0.3-0.5 mL of a 0.1% Epinephrine (Adrenaline) solution diluted in 5 mL of normal saline intramuscularly, subcutaneously, or sublingually. This dose may be repeated every 20 minutes for up to one hour; a second dose may be administered within 5 minutes if clinically indicated. For rapid anti-inflammatory action, administer Prednisolone 90-150 mg intravenously (up to 300 mg if required). Infuse 400-800 mL of crystalloid or colloid solutions (0.9% sodium chloride). In cases of bronchospasm, administer 5-10 mL of 2.4% Aminophylline (Euphylline) intravenously. Continuously monitor blood pressure, pulse, and respiratory status until the emergency medical team arrives.

CONCLUSION AND PREVENTIVE STRATEGIES

The prevention of acute medical emergencies in dental practice requires effective reduction of patient stress and anxiety. Clinicians should implement appropriate premedication strategies, minimize waiting times, select optimal local anesthetic techniques, and carefully monitor blood pressure before and during dental procedures.

To ensure timely emergency intervention, every outpatient dental clinic should maintain a fully accessible emergency drug kit containing the following essential medications:

1. Sodium caffeine benzoate (10-20%);
2. Epinephrine (0.1%);
3. Sterile 0.9% sodium chloride solution;
4. Aminophylline (2.4%);
5. Prednisolone and Hydrocortisone;
6. Phenylephrine (Mesaton 1%);
7. Aqueous ammonia solution (10%);
8. Captopril and Nifedipine;
9. Glucose (40%).

Reference:

1. Робустова, Т.Г. Хирургическая стоматология/Т.Г. Робустова. - 3-е изд., перераб.и доп. - М.: Медицина, 2003. - 504 с.
2. Николаев А.И. Практическая терапевтическая стоматология: учеб. Пособие /А.И.Николаев, Л.М.Цепов 9-е изд. - М.: МЕДпресс - информ , 2013. - 928 с.
3. Учебник/ А.А. Колесов, Н.Н. Каспарова, В.В. Жилина и др. / Под ред. А.А. Колесова - 4 - е изд. Перераб. И доп. - М.: Медицина, 1991. - 464 с.; ил. - Учеб. лит. Для учащихся мед. Институтов).
4. Матешук А.И. Объемы и виды неотложной стоматологической помощи, оказываемой в амбулаторно - поликлинических условиях / А.И. Матешук, В.Д. Вагнер, Р.А. Дистель // Маэстро стоматологии. 2000. - №5. - С.65.
5. Неотложные состояния в амбулаторной и стоматологической практике / П.И. Ивасенко, В.Д. Вагнер, С.В. Скальский и др. - М.: Медицинская книга; Н. Новгород: Изд - во НГМА, 2002. - 115 с.
6. Боровский Е.В. Стоматология: Руководство к практическим занятиям/ Боровский Е.В. Копейкин В.Н. Колесов А.А., Шаргородский А.Г.; Под ред. Проф. Е.В. Боровского.- М.: Медицина. 1987.-528 с.
7. Давыдова Н.В., Фирсова И.В., Суетенков Д.Е., Олейникова Н.М. Профилактика травматических повреждений зубов, мягких тканей, челюстных костей у детей и подростков. Саратовский научно-медицинский журнал. 2011. Т. 7. № 1. С. 199-202. 8. Алямовский В.В., Дуж А.Н., Соколова О.Р., Кан В.В. Анализ обращаемости населения различных возрастных групп в стоматологическую поликлинику. В мире научных открытий. 2013. № 7.3 (43). С. 92-109.
8. Becker, D. E. (2010). Management of immediate allergic reactions: an update for the dental profession. *Anesthesia Progress*, 57(4), 167-178.
9. Guler, N., et al. (2018). Evaluation of emergency situations and development of emergency kits in dental clinics. *Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery*, 76(11), 2251-2259.
10. Malamed, S. F. (2015). *Medical Emergencies in the Dental Office* (7th ed.). Elsevier Health Sciences.
11. Matsura, H. (2020). Systemic complications and their management in geriatric dental patients under local anesthesia. *International Dental Journal*, 70(2), 94-101.
12. Popova, K. A. (2022). Analysis of acute systemic complications in outpatient dental practice. *Russian Journal of Dentistry*, 26(3), 185-192.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №6(5)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.